

1 **Loss-of-function phenomics, ncORFs, and ambiguity of mutant phenotypes in**
2 ***Medicago truncatula***

3 Umut Çakır^{1,2}, Noujoud Gabed³, Selen Kaya⁴, Vagner A. Benedito⁵, Marie Brunet^{6,7}, Xavier
4 Roucou^{7,8}, Igor S. Kryvoruchko⁹

5 ¹Clinical Neuroscience Research Group, Max Planck Institute for Multidisciplinary Sciences,
6 City Campus, Göttingen 37075, Germany

7 ²Georg-August-University, Göttingen 37073, Germany

8 ³Cellular and Molecular Biology Department, Oran High School of Biological Sciences
9 (ESSBO), Oran 31000, Algeria

10 ⁴Department of Molecular Biology and Genetics, Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University,
11 Çanakkale 17020, Turkey

12 ⁵School of Agriculture and Natural Sciences, University of Maryland Eastern Shore, Princess
13 Anne, MD 21853, USA

14 ⁶Department of Pediatrics, Medical Genetics Service, Université de Sherbrooke, Sherbrooke
15 QC J1E4K8, Canada

16 ⁷Centre de Recherche du Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Sherbrooke (CRCHUS),
17 Sherbrooke QC J1E4K8, Canada

18 ⁸Department of Biochemistry and Functional Genomics, Université de Sherbrooke,
19 Sherbrooke QC J1E4K8, Canada

20 ⁹Department of Biology, United Arab Emirates University, P.O. Box 15551, Al Ain, UAE

21 **Correspondence**

22 I. S. Kryvoruchko, Department of Biology, College of Science, United Arab Emirates
23 University, Building F1, Room 0169, P.O. Box 15551, Al Ain, UAE, Tel: +971 3 7136724
24 E-mail: igor.kryvoruchko@uaeu.ac.ae

25 **Running title**

26 Loss-of-function phenomics and ncORFs

27 **Abbreviations**

28 ncORF, non-canonical open reading frame; refORF, reference open reading frame; ncProt,
29 non-canonical protein; refProt, reference protein; mRNA, messenger RNA; ncRNA, non-
30 coding RNA; rRNA, ribosomal RNA; tRNA, transfer RNA; CDS, coding sequence; UTR,
31 untranslated region; aa, amino acids; bp, base pairs; nt, nucleotides; MS, mass spectrometry

32 **SUMMARY**

33 Non-canonical open reading frames (ncORFs) are an emerging area of research that is quickly
34 gaining momentum. Many peptides and proteins missed in initial annotation efforts (ncProts)
35 were subsequently shown to be crucial for a wide range of biological processes. The discovery
36 of ncORFs continues to improve the accuracy of loss-of-function studies because they often
37 occupy the same genomic spaces as annotated ORFs. While databases of mutant phenotypes
38 linked to genomic loci exist in a few species, none of these databases integrate the information
39 on ncORFs present in already characterized loci. In this study, we introduce a nearly
40 comprehensive loss-of-function phenomics dataset of *Medicago truncatula* (673 loci

41 characterized over the past 30 years), which should become an integral part of the genome
42 browser of this organism. We used this dataset to provide a critical analysis of the potential
43 contribution of ncORFs to published phenotypes. We detected mass spectrometry (MS)-
44 validated ncORFs in 10 functionally characterized genes, including major regulators of
45 development and symbiotic relationships. We also found conserved ncORFs in 113
46 characterized genes, including four genes with highly conserved ncORFs. We show that in
47 some studies, the contribution of ncORFs can be ruled out, while in others it cannot. Using
48 real examples, we systematized ambiguities associated with ncORFs. Furthermore, we
49 highlighted little-known trans effects of insertional mutagenesis on splicing as contributors to
50 that ambiguity. Finally, our meta-analysis of published phenotypes reveals that different
51 protein classes have significantly different (unique) proportions of unconditional, conditional,
52 and neutral phenotypes, potentially reflecting their relative functional importance.

53 **Keywords**

54 non-canonical open reading frame, mutant phenotype, phenomics, functional genomics,
55 mass spectrometry proteomics, *MthGSHSb*, *MtKASII*, *MtPHO2-A*, *MtbZIP60b*, purifying
56 selection

57 **Significance statement**

58 This study is the first to merge a nearly comprehensive inventory of loss-of-function studies
59 in a eukaryotic organism with the information on novel MS-validated and conserved ncORFs.

60 **INTRODUCTION**

61 For a long time, functional genomics and genome annotation efforts have primarily been
62 focused on annotated reference proteins (refProts) translated from canonical (reference) open
63 reading frames (refORFs), often overlooking additional coding potential within the same
64 transcripts (Kozak, 1999). Mass spectrometry (MS) proteomics challenged this paradigm
65 through the discovery of the non-canonical proteome (Vanderperre et al., 2013; Mouilleron et
66 al., 2016; Orr et al., 2020; Cardon et al., 2021; Wright et al., 2022). It was deduced from the
67 abundance of high-quality mass spectra that cannot be assigned to refProts (Ning et al., 2010;
68 Pathan et al., 2017). Such a hidden proteome exists even in the smallest culturable bacterium
69 (*Mycoplasma pneumoniae*) with only 729 ORFs (Lluch-Senar et al., 2016). A considerable
70 part of the non-annotated proteome is thought to originate from translation of non-canonical
71 ORFs (ncORFs) to non-canonical peptides and proteins (ncProts). The recognition of the
72 biological relevance of these ncProts is relatively recent (Mouilleron et al., 2016; Orr et al.,
73 2020; Mudge et al., 2022) and has been accelerating in the past few years (Ardern, 2023;
74 Álvarez-Urdiola and Riechmann, 2025; Çakır et al., 2025b; Cardon et al., 2025; Pavesi, 2025;
75 Chang et al., 2025).

76 The ultimate goal of functional genomics studies is to establish accurate relationships between
77 phenotypes and genotypes for the benefit of biomedical research, agriculture, and
78 biotechnology. We can refer to the multitude of such phenotype-genotype units as a phenome.
79 Deducing a true phenome from functional data can be very complex due to the polycistronic
80 nature of eukaryotic transcripts (Mouilleron et al., 2016). Specifically, it introduces a new level
81 of complexity to the interpretation of all functional genomics studies. A ncORF with a biological
82 function can be present on the same RNA molecule together with the refORF. For example, it
83 can be located in a sequence annotated as an untranslated region (UTR) based on the
84 refORF, even though this region may contain a functional coding sequence in any reading
85 frame. For such transcripts, loss-of-function approaches based on post-transcriptional gene
86 silencing, such as RNA interference (RNAi) (Sharp & Zamore, 2000; Baulcombe, 2004;
87 Chaudhary et al., 2024), yield phenotypes that cannot be unequivocally attributed to refProts

88 alone because an RNAi construct simultaneously affects both refProts and ncProts. Insertion-
89 deletion mutagenesis systems such as CRISPR/Cas9 (for Clustered Regularly Interspaced
90 Short Palindromic Repeats [CRISPR] and CRISPR-associated protein 9 [Cas9]; Doudna &
91 Charpentier, 2014; Guo et al., 2023) and retrotransposons (e.g., *Tnt1*, for Transposon of
92 *Nicotiana tabacum*; Tadege et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2018; Kaur et al., 2021) may seem to be
93 more proof against such ambiguity because they can be more selective regarding the target
94 region of a transcript. However, these systems, too, can affect both a refProt and a ncProt,
95 especially if their ORFs overlap and share the same genetic space. In this study, we described
96 a scenario in which insertional mutagenesis affects both ORFs, even if the insertion is located
97 only in a refORF, acting on a ncORF in trans through the effect on splicing (“in trans” because
98 a sequence beyond the immediate insertion site is affected; see Supporting Discussion).
99 Likewise, gain-of-function studies introduce similar ambiguity because an overexpression of a
100 refORF simultaneously overexpresses an embedded ncORF. These considerations call for an
101 objective re-evaluation of published phenotypes in light of the potential contribution of
102 ncORFs.

103 Although very comprehensive phenomics databases have been established for mouse (Wang
104 et al., 2015; Baldarelli et al., 2024), *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Lloyd and Meinke, 2012), and other
105 eukaryotes (Courtier-Orgogozo et al., 2020), none of them considered the contribution of
106 ncORFs so far. Our analysis was conducted using *Medicago truncatula* because it stands out
107 as a model organism. In contrast to *Arabidopsis*, it can establish symbiotic nitrogen fixation
108 (SNF) in association with soil bacteria (rhizobia) and arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) symbiosis
109 with fungi (Barker et al., 1990; Kang et al., 2016; Bandyopadhyay et al., 2019; Nandety et al.,
110 2022). *M. truncatula* has been used as a model for functional genomics since 1995 (Sagan et
111 al., 1995). Despite 30 years in this status, the model has no comprehensive inventory of loss-
112 of-function studies so far. Likewise, a large-scale detection of ncORFs on annotated
113 transcripts had not been conducted in *M. truncatula* until very recently (Çakır et al., 2025b).
114 Even though much attention was paid to the inventory of bioactive peptides in *M. truncatula*
115 (Mergaert et al., 2003; Zhang et al., 2006; Volkening et al., 2012; de Bang et al., 2017; Kereszt
116 et al., 2018; Boschiero et al., 2020), most of them should only conditionally be categorized as
117 ncProts because they originate from transcripts with no annotated long refORFs. Their short
118 ORFs act as refORFs of corresponding transcripts (see supporting data, for example, Data
119 S12).

120 In this study, we filled the knowledge gap about ncORFs, primarily mRNA-ncORFs, in
121 conjunction with published loss-of-function phenotypes attributed to refORFs. We collected
122 information on nearly all such phenotypes linked to specific loci or groups of genes and
123 merged it with data on MS-validated and conserved ncORFs. For the MS validation, we
124 analyzed three large datasets available on ProteomeXchange (Deutsch et al., 2023). They
125 correspond to 16 samples of 10 different organs (PXD002692, Marx et al., 2016; PXD013606,
126 Shin et al., 2021; and PXD022278, Castañeda et al., 2021). To identify conserved ncORFs,
127 we conducted a three-frame global amino acid sequence similarity search of the whole
128 transcriptome of *M. truncatula* using UniProt v. 2020_02 as a subject database (UniProt
129 Consortium, 2019). We deployed a simple, “naïve” approach based on the difference in the
130 number of hits between ncORFs (conservation at the nucleotide level) and corresponding
131 ncProts (conservation at the amino acid level). This way, we detected highly conserved
132 ncORFs under purifying selection in four well-characterized genes, including the master
133 regulator of phosphate homeostasis *MtPHO2-A* (Curtin et al., 2017; Čermák et al., 2017;
134 Huertas et al., 2023). We exemplified the applicability of this “naïve” approach for the large-
135 scale detection of ncORFs that undergo purifying selection. Our analysis permitted
136 discrimination between studies that can rule out the contribution of ncORFs to reported
137 phenotypes and studies in which such ambiguity calls for additional experiments, such as

138 differential mutagenesis of ncORFs and refORFs. By straightforward sequence comparisons,
139 we explained the likely origin of highly conserved ncORFs in five well-characterized genes
140 and showed that strong conservation may not necessarily imply translation of a given ncORF.
141 Instead, some conserved ncORFs are better understood in the context of alternative splicing
142 or gene model structure. Thus, our approach is not only informative for identifying potentially
143 functional ncORFs, but also valuable for refining current gene annotations. Due to space
144 limitations, we placed much of the valuable information about MS-validated and conserved
145 ncORFs into files called Supporting Results and Supporting Discussion. We refer readers to
146 these files for the deep coverage of ncORFs in transcripts characterized by loss-of-function
147 approaches.

148 Our phenomics resource will be useful to the *M. truncatula* community regardless of the
149 ncORF dimension, because it serves the following basic purposes: (1) avoiding the duplication
150 of efforts in studying genes that have already been targeted by other groups; (2) consistency
151 of naming new loci and avoiding redundancy; (3) correction of gene models. It should be noted
152 that despite the very impressive accuracy of the current genome annotation (v. 5.1.9, Pecrix
153 et al., 2018), we found surprisingly large number of cases in which annotation accuracy can
154 be further improved.

155 Lastly, our inferential meta-analysis of loss-of-function phenotypes indicates that diverse
156 protein classes have unique proportions of altered (non-conditional), conditional, and neutral
157 phenotypes, which are significantly different from the overall and specific proportions of
158 functional protein groups in the dataset. These distinct frequencies of phenotypes may reflect
159 the degree of biological importance or functional redundancy of specific groups of proteins.
160 This information can help navigate searches to genes with strong or weak but clear
161 phenotypes by focusing on specific protein classes with high proportions of non-conditional
162 phenotypes. Likewise, it may help prevent misallocation of time and resources in functional
163 genomics or breeding efforts when the likelihood of a given gene to produce a notable
164 phenotype is low. For this reason, our resource is also relevant for applied research and
165 industry, because it can be mined for trait-associated genes, including those involved in
166 symbiosis. This type of information is not available even in the most comprehensive plant
167 phenomics database developed for *A. thaliana* (Lloyd and Meinke, 2012).

168 **RESULTS**

169 **Structure, scope, and general features of the loss-of-function phenomics dataset**

170 Year 2025 marked the 30th anniversary of *M. truncatula* as a model for loss-of-function
171 genomics (Sagan et al., 1995). We conducted a very detailed human curation of 565 loss-of-
172 function studies published between 1995 and 2025. We adopted the style and structure of the
173 first large list of loss-of-function phenotypes of *M. truncatula*, which was compiled by Roy et
174 al. (2020). The list contained 115 loci with SNF phenotypes. We extended the list to 380 loci
175 with SNF phenotypes and 293 loci with non-SNF phenotypes, 673 loci in total (Figure 1).
176 Additional reputable resources contributed to the compilation of our non-SNF list. Especially
177 useful were the review by Kang et al. (2016) and multiple chapters in two books: Cañas and
178 Beltrán (2018) and Sinharoy et al. (2022). Here, it is important to mention a recent review
179 article by Ye et al. (2024). Although we have not used it as a navigator to the original loss-of-
180 function studies, it provides a very comprehensive coverage of functional genomics in *M.*
181 *truncatula*, which is complementary to our discussion.

182 Since *M. truncatula* is primarily a model for studies on SNF, we kept SNF-based lists
183 separately and contrasted them with non-SNF lists in some datasets. While importing the
184 information about the 115 loci from Supplemental Dataset 1 of Roy et al. (2020), we rechecked

185 each phenotype using an approach centered on *M. truncatula*, which resulted in some minor
186 differences between our dataset and the dataset of Roy et al. (2020). We added a column with
187 the current locus identifiers (genome annotation v. 5.1.9). Deducing this information was often
188 difficult because not all studies provided an easy means of identifying the targeted genes. We
189 had to conduct careful analysis of primer sequences, RNAi constructs, *Tnt1* flanking sequence
190 tags (FSTs), and other data to find the exact correspondence of studied loci with gene models
191 of the current genome release. Despite these efforts, it was not possible to ascertain the locus
192 identifiers of seven characterized genes: *MtCIR2*, *MtCRA1*, *MtGLYI*, *MtLAL*, *MtLHCB1.4*,
193 *MtLYK2bis*, and *MtLYK5bis*. Three of them are likely to exist only in the ecotype R108:
194 *MtGLYI*, *MtLYK2bis*, and *MtLYK5bis*. The sequence of *MtCIR2* was kindly provided by the
195 authors (Zhao et al., 2023). However, it has no corresponding gene model in the latest release
196 of the genome annotation. Locus *MtuORF1p* is a special case. It is an upstream ORF (uORF)
197 located in the 5'-UTR of a characterized transcription factor *MtNF-YA1/MtHAP2-1* (Combiér
198 et al., 2006, 2008). These eight genetic units, specifically, *MtCIR2*, *MtCRA1*, *MtGLYI*, *MtLAL*,
199 *MtLHCB1.4*, *MtLYK2bis*, *MtLYK5bis*, and the uORF *MtuORF1p* found in the transcript of
200 *MtNF-YA1/MtHAP2-1*, were excluded from the count of unique locus identifiers (673 unique
201 loci listed but 681 cistrons described; uORF *MtuORF1p* and *MtNF-YA1/MtHAP2-1* are two
202 different cistrons of a single locus). Consequently, these eight loci are also excluded from all
203 figures and most datasets. Details of corresponding phenotypes of these and other genes can
204 be found in Data S1-S6.

205 It should be noted that studies describing mutants with no linked genetic loci were beyond the
206 scope of our analysis. Thus, the few mutants mentioned above (for example, mutants of
207 *MtCIR2* and *MtCRA1*) are an exception because their corresponding loci were thought to be
208 known. Data S1 (non-SNF refORFs) and Data S2 (non-SNF ncORFs) contain information on
209 refORFs and ncORFs associated with non-SNF phenotypes, respectively. Data S3 (SNF
210 refORFs) and Data S4 (SNF ncORFs) provide the corresponding information for SNF
211 phenotypes. Data S5 lists genes studied both for SNF and non-SNF phenotypes. Data S6
212 combines the information on all 681 genes studied by loss-of-function approaches. Data S7
213 contains references for loss-of-function studies. Data S8 is reserved for references describing
214 gain-of-function phenotypes of ncORFs. Our core dataset consists of six Excel files described
215 in Table 1. Although our study focused on loss-of-function phenotypes, an exception was
216 made for characterized ncORFs. To provide a deeper functional description of ncORFs, we
217 also included gain-of-function phenotypes in Data S2 and S4. However, all other datasets in
218 our study are based exclusively on loss-of-function phenotypes. The complete list of datasets
219 pertinent to this study is shown in Table 2 (Data S7-S19). Data S10 and S11 are of special
220 importance because they can be used as “cheat-sheets” by functional genomics specialists
221 and researchers in the industry. Specifically, the lists can predict the likelihood of a gene giving
222 a scorable phenotype. Data S12 is a master table listing and analyzing characterized loci that
223 have MS-validated and/or conserved ncORFs.

224 **The critical need for a comprehensive loss-of-function phenomics dataset in *M.*** 225 ***truncatula***

226 The progress of functional genomics in *M. truncatula* has been greatly accelerated by the
227 insertional mutagenesis using tobacco retrotransposon *Tnt1* (Tadege et al., 2008; Lee et al.,
228 2018; Kaur et al., 2021), although the toolkit is not limited to this system (Grandbastien et al.,
229 1989; Mazier et al., 2007; Cui et al., 2013; Vives et al., 2016). Over the past five years, on
230 average, nearly 47 new genes have been characterized by loss-of-function approaches each
231 year (Figure 1). With the advent of CRISPR/Cas9 (Doudna & Charpentier, 2014; Guo et al.,
232 2023), this number will hopefully rise further each year. The total number of genes with
233 information on mutant phenotypes reached 673 by 16 June 2025, which is only a fraction of

234 the corresponding number of genes characterized in *Arabidopsis* (Lloyd and Meinke, 2012).
235 Nevertheless, 673 is the number large enough to require systematic recording, curation, and
236 meta-analysis.

237 The lack of a standardized protocol for collecting and displaying information on newly
238 characterized genes compromised the status of *M. truncatula* as a functionally annotated
239 model. When a researcher identifies a gene that looks interesting for the functional analysis,
240 one of the first questions is whether it has already been studied. Unfortunately, this information
241 is not readily available for 60% of genes out of 673 characterized so far (Figure 2a; Data S6).
242 In this context, it is important to emphasize the central role of the *M. truncatula* genome
243 browser v. 5 developed in 2018 (Pecrix et al., 2018). This indispensable resource is the hub
244 linking many types of data and displaying them in a well-organized, user-friendly format for
245 the maximal benefit of the *Medicago* community. However, integrating old and new functional
246 genomics data into the genome browser is a major technical challenge. This is because the
247 truly comprehensive and error-free process of collecting such data cannot be easily
248 automated. For example, it is very unlikely to be efficiently outsourced to artificial intelligence.
249 The team curating the browser made an enormous effort and accurately referenced loss-of-
250 function studies for 269 genes, which is 40% of the total (Figure 2a; Data S6, “Yes” in Columns
251 V and W). Unfortunately, 173 genes (26%) completely evaded the functional annotation
252 (Figure 2b; Data S6, “No” in Columns V and W), while 218 genes (32%) were provided with
253 references that do not inform the users about the corresponding loss-of-function analyses
254 (Figure 2a, categories “Yes/YN” and “No/YN”; Data S6, “NY” in Column W). Naturally, newer
255 studies tend to be missed at a higher rate compared to older ones. For example, more than
256 half of genes functionally characterized since 2023 are not labeled as such by the end of July
257 2025 (Data S6 Column W). However, the population of 173 “missed” genes (“No/No” category
258 in Figure 2a) extends in time back to 2001, with 81 genes characterized more than five years
259 ago (Figure 2b; Data S6). This lack of integration into the browser, even years after the original
260 publication, reflects the difficulty of manual curation of such data. We found no bias toward
261 any method, phenotype, or protein class among those “missed” genes. They were overlooked
262 simply due to the lack of a centralized system integrating all functional data into the browser.

263 These observations strongly suggest the need for such a system. Possibly, it could be
264 developed with a Wikipedia-like format, with authors encouraged or obligatorily requested to
265 enter all relevant information about genes at the time they are submitted for publication. One
266 reason for such an open format is the difficulty of allocating this task to a specific
267 researcher/curating team member. Because dozens of new genes are characterized each
268 year, keeping functional data up to date requires significant and continuous effort. For
269 example, for our team, it took nearly three years to collect and systematize information about
270 673 genes. This problem can be efficiently addressed by agreeing upon a set of rules and
271 implementing these rules for all researchers who publish functional characterization studies
272 on *M. truncatula* genes. Our dataset can be the basis for such a system, which can be further
273 developed in real time as more genes are characterized each year.

274 **Specific examples where a unified loss-of-function database could help avoid** 275 **redundancy and confusion**

276 An important question is whether this lack of functional annotation had any negative impact
277 on studies in *M. truncatula*. Can we find examples of such impact through the meta-analysis
278 of our dataset? Unfortunately, yes. Column X (Notes) in Data S6 describes a few such
279 instances. They are categorized below.

280 **Multiple names for the same gene: potential duplication of efforts**

281 The first loss-of-function study on locus MtrunA17_Chr5g0422541 (*MtAOC1*) was published
282 in 2005 (Isayenkov et al., 2005). Recently, a different team characterized this gene very
283 completely, too, and named it *MtAOC2* (Yang et al., 2023). Both studies were published in
284 Plant Physiology and covered different aspects. The second team, and the editor of the
285 journal, were unaware of the 18-year-old study on this gene. It is evident that no researcher
286 or editor would ever wish to miss such important information by the time of the intended
287 publication, or ideally much earlier. Had it been available through a centralized resource, it
288 would greatly facilitate planning, experimental design, and manuscript writing for the second
289 team and would have avoided confusion for anyone wishing to study this gene in the future.
290 The fact that this gene was targeted by two high-quality studies is still not reflected in the
291 genome browser, which exemplifies the difficulty of manual curation of such data. To further
292 complicate the situation, other loci were called *MtAOC2* (MtrunA17_Chr7g0220911) by
293 Isayenkov et al. (2005) and *MtAOC1* (MtrunA17_Chr4g0034431) by Yang et al. (2023), neither
294 of which were targeted by loss-of-function studies so far. Developing a consistent and non-
295 redundant set of gene names is another important and challenging task that can be addressed
296 efficiently by a unified resource.

297 Another locus with a similar fate is MtrunA17_Chr8g0343011. It was called *MtLOX9* in the first
298 loss-of-function study (Li et al., 2022), *MtLOX24* in the second, unrelated study (Xu et al.,
299 2024), and *MtLOX4* in the genome browser v. 5.1.9. Like in the first example, the authors of
300 the second study were unaware of the previous work on this gene, which is not referenced in
301 the genome browser. It may be argued that the problem is minor because the groups studied
302 different processes. However, under certain circumstances, funding, time, and material
303 resources could be wasted by duplicating earlier efforts. This possibility should serve as a
304 motivation for the research community to establish a system that integrates all loss-of-function
305 data into corresponding genome browsers, not only for *M. truncatula*.

306 **One name for multiple genes: ambiguity**

307 A case of the opposite type can be exemplified by studies that gave the same name to different
308 and sometimes unrelated loci. *MtCHS* was a name given to three different genes:
309 MtrunA17_Chr7g0252331 (Zhang et al., 2009), MtrunA17_Chr7g0220211 (Samac et al.,
310 2011), and MtrunA17_Chr1g0201391 (Cook et al., 2025). None of these loci are named or
311 referenced in the genome browser v. 5.1.9. Other examples are the loci called *MtMYB1* and
312 *MtbZIP60* in original articles. *MtMYB1* is MtrunA17_Chr7g0242521 in Floss et al. (2017) but
313 MtrunA17_Chr3g0080861 in Li et al. (2022). *MtbZIP60* is MtrunA17_Chr1g0171291 in Ribeiro
314 et al. (2022) but MtrunA17_Chr4g0035414 in Xing et al. (2024). Only one of them is correctly
315 referenced in the genome browser v. 5.1.9 (*MtMYB1*, Floss et al., 2017). To avoid confusion,
316 we added lowercase letters to the names of these seven genes, in the chronological order
317 (*MtCHSa*, *MtCHSb*, *MtCHSc*; *MtMYB1a*, *MtMYB1b*; *MtbZIP60a*, *MtbZIP60b*, respectively).
318 *MtSymSCL1* was a name given to locus MtrunA17_Chr1g0183641 by Kim & Nam (2013) and
319 locus MtrunA17_Chr4g0057891 by Rey et al. (2017). In the current dataset, we use alternative
320 names of these genes: *MtSCL2* and *MtRAD1*, respectively, which are correctly named and
321 referenced in the genome browser v. 5.1.9.

322 **Converging acronyms: even more ambiguity**

323 The loci *MtCRA1* and *MtCRA2* fall into a special sub-category. In contrast to the genes
324 mentioned above, these names were given to unrelated loci. A locus with still unknown identity
325 (Data S6) was called *MtCRA1* for COMPACT ROOT ARCHITECTURE 1 (Scholte et al. 2002;
326 Laffont et al., 2010). Locus MtrunA17_Chr3g0140861 was named *MtCRA2* (the same
327 acronym) in Huault et al. (2014) and several subsequent studies. However, two other genes
328 were named *MtCRA1* and *MtCRA2* for CHITINASE-RELATED AGGLUTININ 1 and 2,

329 respectively (Data S6), although they have not been targeted by loss-of-function studies so
330 far (Tian et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2016a). Thus, their names are not revised and were not
331 included in the current dataset.

332 **Incorrect locus naming in the genome browser v. 5.1.9**

333 We found numerous examples of gene names that conflict with naming from original loss-of-
334 function studies. We summarized these examples in Tables 3 and S1. At least 11 names were
335 incorrectly assigned to other loci in the genome browser v. 5.1.9. These names were already
336 used for genes characterized by loss-of-function approaches. Two names, *MtChOMT1* and
337 *MtPRP1*, were misassigned to two genes each. For example, MtrunA17_Chr8g0366751 is the
338 locus ID of a gene called *MtMYC2* by Guo et al. (2024). However, in the genome browser, a
339 different member of this family was named *MtMYC2*: MtrunA17_Chr5g0411341. This gene
340 was called *MtBHLH2* by Deng et al. (2019) (see Data S1, Data S3, and Table S1). These
341 examples further emphasize the need for a unified resource that would implement and
342 regulate gene naming based on original publications or some other systematic principle.

343 **Splitting one characterized gene model into two**

344 Genome annotation is a dynamic process. Naturally, some older gene models characterized
345 some time ago do not correspond to a single locus in the current genome annotation (v. 5.1.9).
346 Such models are now split into two loci each. This is relevant to the annotation of these loci
347 because it introduces functional ambiguity. Deciding which of two resulting loci was affected
348 in an original study is not a trivial task. In some cases, both loci might have been affected. In
349 a unified system proposed here, such a decision may require an independent expert who re-
350 examines the original data. Alternatively, it can be based on the manual input of a team that
351 produced the data. In this article, we simply draw attention to such models, with a few
352 examples.

353 Functional analysis of v4 locus Medtr7g113890 (*MtGSHSa*) was conducted more than 20
354 years ago (Frendo et al., 2001, 2005). Now this gene model is split into two loci:
355 MtrunA17_Chr7g0273151 and MtrunA17_Chr7g0273161. Which of these two transcripts was
356 affected by two antisense constructs in the original study? Probably both, even though they
357 share no sequence similarity. Although the article provides no sequence data of their
358 constructs, the mRNA of locus MtrunA17_Chr7g0273151 was likely to be co-affected with a
359 related locus MtrunA17_Chr7g0273131 by the shorter of the two antisense constructs (1.1 kb)
360 because this pair has 76% identity over the length of 859 nt. The mRNA of the second locus,
361 MtrunA17_Chr7g0273161, was probably co-affected with a related locus
362 MtrunA17_Chr7g0273141 by the longer of antisense constructs (1.8 kb) because this pair has
363 75% identity over the length of 815 nt. Thus, the reported phenotype can be attributed to all
364 four loci unless a dedicated study shows otherwise. Unfortunately, this information is not
365 reflected in the genome browser v. 5.1.9, nor is the fact that the loci were targeted by a loss-
366 of-function approach. In this and a few other cases, we attempted to fill this gap by assigning
367 unique but related names to these loci (*MtGSHSa* and *MthGSHSa*; *MtGSHSb* and
368 *MthGSHSb*, respectively). Specifically for these homologs, we modified the original names
369 introduced by Frendo et al. (2001, 2005), where “h” stands for “homo”. They are fully explained
370 in Supporting Results. This group of genes presents special interest to our study and will be
371 discussed in detail in the context of ncORFs (Data S12 to S14 and Data S16).

372 The second v4 locus of this type is Medtr4g088055 (*MtROP7*, Wang et al., 2021), which is
373 now split into MtrunA17_Chr4g0046211 and MtrunA17_Chr4g0046221. These two loci are
374 separated by only one nucleotide (A) in the plus-strand and share no sequence identity. We
375 propose names *MtROP7a* and *MtROP7b*, respectively, for these loci. RNAi constructs used

376 in the original study (Wang et al., 2021) target the first locus (*MtROP7a*) together with many
377 other genes, including *MtROP8* and *MtROP10*. The alignment of these RNAi constructs with
378 the second locus (*MtROP7b*) yields no obvious similarity, except for a 40-nt-long region having
379 88% identity with the RNAi construct produced by primers Forward (MROP10) 1 and Reverse
380 (MROP10) 1 (Supplemental Table 2 in Wang et al., 2021). Is this very local similarity sufficient
381 to affect *MtROP7b*? Probably not, because much longer sequences (>130 nt) are typically
382 used for efficient RNAi-mediated silencing in plants (Kakiyama et al., 2019). Only the
383 *MtROP7b*-specific qRT-PCR analysis can tell. With so little evidence linking this gene to the
384 conditional phenotype reported by Wang et al. (2021), *MtROP7b* would be removed from our
385 dataset as being unaffected by the loss-of-function experiment. However, the following
386 consideration shows how important it is to look deeper into such examples and to inspect the
387 original qRT-PCR data on a case-by-case basis. Analysis of *MtROP7*-designed qRT-PCR
388 primers used by Wang et al. (2021) clearly shows that the new model is wrong and the old
389 one (v4) is correct (Supplemental Table 2 in Wang et al., 2021). The forward primer
390 (TTATGCTCCAAATGTGCCTA) is located in *MtROP7a* whereas the reverse primer
391 (TGTTTTAGAGCTGCACTCA) resides in *MtROP7b*. They can form an amplicon of 269 bp
392 exclusively from the cDNA of the old model. If the signal reported in Figure S5 of Wang et al.
393 (2021) had come from contamination with genomic DNA, the amplicon would have been 401
394 bp long because of Intron 4. The melting curve analysis would certainly have alerted the
395 researchers about such contamination. Thus, the reported data is very likely to be correct and
396 unambiguous. This is not the only example of a “longer” original model making more sense
397 because of being supported either by transcriptomic or by MS proteomic data (see the
398 example of *MthGSHSb* in Data S16 Slide 7). Nevertheless, it is important to look deeper into
399 the reason for rejecting the old model by the current genome annotation. The 58-bp-long
400 junction between the ORFs of *MtROP7a* and *MtROP7b* is free of stop codons only in frame 3
401 relative to the sequences, which is not the reading frame of the annotated ORFs. Thus, the
402 sequences are separated by in-frame stop codons. Possibly, the junction is a spliced-out
403 intron, which could explain why in-frame stop codons in this region were tolerated by natural
404 selection. It is worth noting that neither of these two loci is currently provided with the correct
405 reference in the genome browser v. 5.1.9 (Data S6).

406 Another example of this sort is v4 locus Medtr4g073400 (*MtSYT1*, Gavrin et al., 2017), which
407 is now split into MtrunA17_Chr4g0037111 and MtrunA17_Chr4g0037121 (*MtSYT1a* and
408 *MtSYT1b*, respectively, in our dataset). As in the case of *MtROP7*, the loci are separated by
409 a single nucleotide (A) in the plus-strand. Likewise, qRT-PCR primers MtSyt1-F
410 AGGAGGCCCGTTGGAATTTT and MtSyt1-R GTGATGCTTCCCCTCAACA (Supplementary
411 Table 1 in Gavrin et al., 2017) span the junction between the two loci, forming an amplicon of
412 625 bp from both cDNA and genomic DNA, according to the new model. The length of 625 bp
413 is clearly suboptimal for qRT-PCR (normal range is between 60 and 150 bp, Udvardi et al.,
414 2008). Evidently, the qRT-PCR signal shown in Supplementary Figure 7 of Gavrin et al. (2017)
415 could come from the cDNA corresponding to the “old” model, if the junction that contains in-
416 frame stop codons was spliced out. We doubt that the qRT-PCR settings used in that high-
417 quality study would permit the generation of a signal exclusively from the contamination with
418 genomic DNA, which would result in this unusually long amplicon (625 bp). For this reason, in
419 our dataset, we consider *MtSYT1a* and *MtSYT1b* as part of the same functional unit, as it was
420 described in the original study. If the new model is correct, it is impossible to find out if both
421 loci were affected by the generic RNAi construct designed for simultaneous silencing of
422 *MtSYT1* and *MtSYT3*, which share no sequence identity. This is because RNAi primers
423 MtSyt1-F TGGATCCATCACAGGCCATG and MtSyt1-R CGCAAACGGATTTGTGTGGT
424 (Supplementary Table 1 in Gavrin et al., 2017) do not perfectly match the cDNA of the split
425 models MtrunA17_Chr4g0037111 and MtrunA17_Chr4g0037121. Thus, functional ambiguity

426 does not permit exclusion of either locus from the reported RNAi phenotype even though only
427 MtrunA17_Chr4g0037111 is currently provided with the correct reference in the genome
428 browser v. 5.1.9 (Data S6).

429 The last example of a split locus is v4 model Medtr1g102190 (*MtLICK1*, Wang et al., 2025). It
430 corresponds to two adjacent loci in the genome assembly v. 5.1.9: MtrunA17_Chr1g0204221
431 and MtrunA17_Chr1g0204231 (*MtLICK1a* and *MtLICK1b*, respectively, in our dataset). They
432 are separated by a nucleotide triplet ACA in the minus-strand. If this newer model is correct,
433 only MtrunA17_Chr1g0204221 was affected by the *Tnt1* insertion in Wang et al., 2025. Based
434 on FST NF9810_low_9 (the *Tnt1* mutant collection, Tadege et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2018; Kaur
435 et al., 2021), the insertion is located in the 5'-UTR of this gene. However, locus
436 MtrunA17_Chr1g0204221 is a direct continuation of locus MtrunA17_Chr1g0204231. The
437 high similarity of exon-intron structures shown in Extended Data Fig. 2k and i (Wang et al.,
438 2025) suggests that the new model may be incorrect. Thus, the insertion is predicted to be in
439 the last exon of the v4 model. If it were the 5'-UTR, the mutant phenotype would probably not
440 differ from the wild type. The study provided further proof for the validity of the original model
441 by MS proteomics. Specifically, Table 1 in Wang et al. (2025), which illustrates MtLICK1
442 phosphorylation sites, lists a peptide MSI(pT)VGAAEGLAYLHHEANPHIIHR with the original
443 position of the phosphorylation site at T151. It maps to the 3'-UTR of
444 MtrunA17_Chr1g0204231 in such a way that 306 nt located between MSITVGAAEGLA and
445 YLHHEANPHIIHR in the current model are missing. The same concerns peptides
446 RM(pS)ITVGAAEGLAYLHHEANPHIIHR (S149) and
447 RMSITVGAAEGLA(pY)LHHEANPHIIHR (Y160). This indicates that this part of the junction
448 between MtrunA17_Chr1g0204231 and MtrunA17_Chr1g0204221 is a spliced-out intron, like
449 in the cases of *MtROP7* and possibly *MtSYT1*. In contrast, peptides DIKA(pS)NVLLDTEFQAK
450 (S177) and ASNVLLD(pT)EFQAK (T183) map exactly to the junction site between
451 MtrunA17_Chr1g0204231 and MtrunA17_Chr1g0204221, which means this region is a
452 translated exon. Thus, we consider MtrunA17_Chr1g0204231 and MtrunA17_Chr1g0204221
453 as a single functional unit in our dataset, as it was described in the original study.
454 Unfortunately, neither of these loci is provided with the correct reference in the genome
455 browser v. 5.1.9 (Data S6).

456 **Duplicated gene models**

457 A different type of challenge in assigning a mutant phenotype to an annotated locus is
458 exemplified by a v4 gene Medtr4g125520. It corresponds to two entries in the genome
459 assembly v. 5.1.9: MtrunA17_Chr4g0070611 and MtrunA17_Chr4g0070641. In contrast to the
460 splitting of an old model into two, as described in the previous section, these two loci are
461 separated by several other genes and repeat elements. Although the gDNA sequences of
462 MtrunA17_Chr4g0070611 and MtrunA17_Chr4g0070641 are identical base-for-base over the
463 shared region, the loci are located in separate genomic positions. The shorter locus
464 (MtrunA17_Chr4g0070641) entirely lacks the region corresponding to the end of Exon 3 of
465 MtrunA17_Chr4g0070611. The gene model presented in Figure 5a of Liu et al. (2014)
466 corresponds to MtrunA17_Chr4g0070611. Thus, only this longer locus is listed in the current
467 dataset. However, if both models are correct, it is impossible to tell which one was affected by
468 the *Tnt1* insertions because the gDNA sequences around the insertion sites are identical in
469 these two genes.

470 We attempted to solve this ambiguity by analyzing FST sequences of *Tnt1* insertions
471 corresponding to lines *myb14-1* and *myb14-2* (Figure 5a of Liu et al., 2014). These are FSTs
472 NF14565_low_42 and NF0084-INSERTION-2, respectively, both in reverse orientation. The
473 first FST is not informative for our purpose because its end reaches only 14 bp upstream of

474 the translational start (ATG) codon of MtrunA17_Chr4g0070611 and
475 MtrunA17_Chr4g0070641. These 14 bp do not match the gDNA of either locus in the
476 Jemalong A17-based genome browser v. 5.1.9. They are likely to present a sequencing error
477 because they also do not match a corresponding model in the ecotype R108 (the background
478 of the *Tnt1* mutant population; Tadege et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2018; Kaur et al., 2021). The
479 second FST, NF0084-INSERTION-2, gives more information because its end reaches 612 bp
480 upstream of the ATG. While corresponding regions in the Jemalong A17 genome are identical
481 between MtrunA17_Chr4g0070611 and MtrunA17_Chr4g0070641, there is a single matching
482 sequence in the R108 genome. It is immediately upstream of a gene nearly identical to
483 MtrunA17_Chr4g0070611 at the gDNA level (only three mismatches over the entire length of
484 MtrunA17_Chr4g0070611). Thus, we conclude that the second (short) copy may exist in the
485 ecotype Jemalong A17 but is absent from the ecotype R108, which suggests a very recent
486 duplication. This is further supported by the qRT-PCR-mediated test for gene copy number
487 presented in Supplemental Figure S11 of Liu et al. (2014). Primers MtMYB14qPCR1-F
488 AGGCAACATATCCTCAGATGAAG and MtMYB14qPCR1-R
489 TCGTGTTC AATAATTCTTGATTTC A (Supplemental Table 4, Liu et al., 2014) reside in a
490 region shared between MtrunA17_Chr4g0070611 and MtrunA17_Chr4g0070641. The signal
491 generated by these primers corresponds to a single genomic copy. This is an example leaving
492 a big question about the functional status of both loci in Jemalong A17: which of them is a
493 functional ortholog of the single copy in R108? Even with a targeted mutagenesis tool such as
494 CRISPR/Cas9 it may be challenging to discriminate between these loci because of the high
495 nucleotide identity within, upstream, and downstream of the sequences. Future functional
496 annotation of such loci should probably indicate ambiguities related to the differences between
497 the genomes of ecotypes A17 and R108.

498 **Loss-of-function methodology and biological processes studied in *M. truncatula***

499 Diverse methods were used for loss-of-function analyses of 673 *M. truncatula* genes (22
500 approaches, Figure S1). More than half of the studies applied one (or a combination) of just
501 two methods: insertional mutagenesis of tobacco retrotransposon *Tnt1* (359 genes) (Tadege
502 et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2018; Kaur et al., 2021) and post-transcriptional silencing mediated by
503 RNAi (265 genes) (Sharp & Zamore, 2000; Baulcombe, 2004; Chaudhary et al., 2024). As a
504 new method, gene editing with the aid of CRISPR/Cas9 (Doudna & Charpentier, 2014; Guo
505 et al., 2023) was used for only 87 genes so far. The popularity of RNAi as a tool is remarkable
506 given the known limitations and ambiguity associated with this method. Technically, it is a
507 simple and inexpensive approach when the generation of transgenic roots (so-called hairy
508 roots, Nilsson & Olsson, 1997; Limpens et al., 2004), rather than the entire transgenic plants,
509 is sufficient for the analysis. Out of 117 genes first characterized in 2023-2025, 30 were
510 studied by RNAi, which is almost the same as the number of genes studied by CRISPR/Cas9
511 in the same period (31 genes). *Tnt1* was used for more than half of the 117 genes (67 genes),
512 followed by FNB (11 genes), EMS (four genes), and AS (one gene) in the same period. FNB,
513 EMS, and AS stand for Fast Neutron Bombardment mutagenesis (Li et al., 2001), Ethyl
514 Methanesulfonate mutagenesis (Sega, 1984), and Antisense-mediated gene silencing
515 (Waterhouse et al., 1998), respectively. From this data, it is evident that the *Tnt1* resource
516 plays a pivotal role in the functional genomics of *M. truncatula* (Data S6, Figure S1).

517 *M. truncatula* was used for studies on 97 biological processes (Data S9, Figure S2). However,
518 this legume was primarily established as a model for SNF. More than half of 673 genes were
519 tested for SNF (380 genes), followed by root development (166 genes), and AM (141 genes).
520 Among non-symbiotic processes other than root development, *M. truncatula* was frequently
521 tested for leaf development (104 genes), flower development (60 genes), control of body size
522 (48 genes), floral transition (48 genes), and pod development (40 genes). Seed-related studies

523 are also numerous in *M. truncatula* (93 genes): seed development (47 genes), seed
524 composition (27 genes), seed germination (8 genes), seed longevity (5 genes), seed coat
525 function (3 genes), and seed dormancy (3 genes).

526 **More than half of the genes studied in *M. truncatula* are transcription factors and**
527 **enzymes**

528 Transcription factors (TFs) and enzymes are two protein groups prevailing in the current
529 dataset (224 and 205 genes, respectively). Counts of these and other protein groups are
530 shown in Figure 3, Figure S3, Data S10, and Data S11. Among TFs, the top four most
531 represented families are AP2-EREBP (21 genes), GRAS (19 genes), MYB-HB-like (18 genes),
532 and SBP (17 genes). Among enzymes, the most represented classes are kinases (48 genes),
533 oxidoreductases (45 genes), transferases (43 genes), and hydrolases (39 genes). Given the
534 pivotal role of transport proteins in SNF, AM, and other biological processes, transporters (73
535 genes) and channels (13 genes) are also well-represented in the current dataset. Remarkably,
536 transport substrates were found for many of these proteins (60 transporters and 7 channels),
537 which is usually a challenging task.

538 **Non-conditional loss-of-function phenotypes are found in 62% of genes studied in *M.***
539 ***truncatula***

540 We have categorized phenotypes of 673 genes studied by loss-of-function approaches into
541 three categories. This classification was based exclusively on the genetic conditions.
542 Specifically, it did not consider conditions such as different growth media or temperature
543 regimes. Phenotypes caused by single genes were categorized as non-conditional (A for
544 altered). Phenotypes caused by more than one gene were regarded as conditional (C for
545 conditional). Neutral phenotypes (N for neutral) were those that did not differ from the wild
546 type, regardless of the number of genes affected in each line. The overall proportions of A-,
547 C-, and N-phenotypes were 62%, 27%, and 11%, respectively (Figure S4). However, these
548 proportions differed slightly between SNF phenotypes and non-SNF phenotypes (compare
549 Figures S4a and S4b). The proportion of C-phenotypes was higher among genes tested for
550 SNF (31%), compared to non-SNF phenotypes (26%). At the same time, the proportions of N-
551 phenotypes did not differ much (16% and 15% for SNF and non-SNF, respectively). Only 53%
552 of genes tested for SNF gave non-conditional phenotypes (A-phenotypes), which suggests
553 functional redundancy due to the robust structure of the genetic program controlling SNF.

554 This relatively low “success rate” of loss-of-function studies on SNF reflects the challenge in
555 identifying crucial genes that can be used for the improvement of SNF in legume crops and
556 synthetic biology efforts to make non-legume plants undergo SNF. With some effort, Data S6
557 can help predict the likely “success rate” of planned loss-of-function studies for specific
558 biological processes, as we showed for SNF. For example, all 11 genes tested for cold stress
559 showed an A-phenotype for this biological process (higher sensitivity or lower sensitivity).
560 Hence, other genes possibly involved in cold stress are likely to have scorable A-phenotypes,
561 too. In contrast, out of 60 genes tested for flower development, not more than half exhibited
562 A-phenotypes. Because Data S6 organizes phenotypes at the gene level, additional
563 processing is required to examine them in the context of individual biological processes tested
564 in each study. In the next section, we focus on statistically significant differences in this
565 “success rate” among different protein classes and groups of classes. Extracting this
566 information from Data S6 is simple because phenotypic categories are linked to genes.
567 Moreover, we find this type of data more relevant for academic research and breeding efforts
568 because it can tell which gene groups are more likely to yield a scorable phenotype.

569 In the remaining part of this section, we present data on the agreement between phenotypic
570 categories when the same genes are tested for SNF and non-SNF phenotypes (Figure S5).
571 Among 219 genes tested for SNF and at least one non-SNF phenotype (Data S5), 40% had
572 A-phenotypes for both processes (group AA). For conditional (CC) and neutral (NN)
573 phenotypes, this proportion was 25% and 5%, respectively (Figure S5). Cases of discordance
574 regarding phenotypic categories were not very prominent among genes tested for both types
575 of biological processes. The largest discordance group (10%) was represented by genes that
576 exhibited A-phenotypes when tested for non-SNF processes and N-phenotypes when tested
577 for SNF (group AN in Figure S5). The reciprocal group, NA, accounts for only 5% of 219 genes,
578 which emphasizes that purely SNF-specific genes are not very abundant. These observations
579 suggest the relatively large number of genes with pleiotropic effects, as can be seen also for
580 various non-SNF phenotypes in Data S6. In summary, the chance that a gene selected for
581 analysis will give an A-phenotype for at least one biological process is 62% (Figure S4c). If a
582 gene shows an A-phenotype for SNF, in 40% of cases, it will also have a scorable A-phenotype
583 for at least one non-SNF process (Figure S5b). This may reflect the adoption of non-symbiotic
584 genes for symbiotic processes reported in many studies (Limpens et al., 2003; Soyano et al.,
585 2019; Huisman & Geurts, 2019; Liu & Bisseling, 2020; Hawkins & Oresnik, 2022).

586 **Unique proportions of phenotypic categories in different protein classes may reflect** 587 **their relative functional importance**

588 As shown in Figure 3, the proportions of phenotypic categories are not the same for different
589 protein classes. Likewise, different groups of combined protein classes have different
590 proportions of phenotypic categories (Figure S3). The natural question is whether these
591 differences are statistically significant. Data S10 and S11 present statistical analyses of these
592 differences for protein classes and larger groups, respectively. Sheet "Sorted by count" in Data
593 S10 shows which classes have A:C:N ratios significantly different from the overall ratio of
594 62:27:11 (see also Figure S4c). Four classes differ significantly from that ratio: TFs of the SBP
595 family and the C2C2-Dof family, channels with unknown substrates, and protease inhibitors.
596 TFs of the SBP family have the ratio of 6:94:0, which corresponds to 16 out of 17 tested SBP
597 genes having C-phenotypes. This, however, is a special case because nearly all these SBP
598 genes were affected by miRNA in a single study (Wang et al., 2019). A somewhat similar
599 situation is observed in TFs of the C2C2-Dof family (the ratio of 8:0:92), where 12 out of 13
600 genes were targeted in a single study (Zhang et al., 2019). In contrast to the SBP family, these
601 genes were targeted in separate *Tnt1* lines and exhibited N-phenotypes. Channels with
602 unknown substrates fall into the same category (the ratio of 17:0:83), with four out of seven
603 genes targeted in a single study (Charpentier et al., 2016). Protease inhibitors have the ratio
604 of 20:0:80, with four out of five genes exhibiting N-phenotypes. Much more interesting
605 differences are observed when individual classes are cross-compared with each other rather
606 than with the overall ratio of 62:27:11. Sheet "Example comparisons" in Data S10 highlights
607 highly significant differences between related classes such as kinases and oxidoreductases,
608 transferases and hydrolases, TFs of the AP2-EREBP family and the MYB-HB-like family, etc.
609 For example, kinases have a much higher proportion of A-phenotypes compared to
610 oxidoreductases and a much lower proportion of N-phenotypes, which reflects their crucial
611 roles in various processes. Likewise, TFs of the MYB-HB-like family have a much higher
612 proportion of A-phenotypes compared to other TF groups, such as the AP2-EREBP family and
613 the GRAS family. TFs of the AP2-EREBP family have an unusually high proportion of C-
614 phenotypes (57%) but no N-phenotypes among 21 tested genes. This information can be of
615 use for practical purposes because it provides a quantitative measure of relative functional
616 importance and redundancy.

617 When combined functional groups are considered (Data S11), similar significant differences
618 are evident. Channels stand out as a group with the A:C:N ratio of 62:0:38, which is
619 significantly different from the overall ratio of 62:27:11. They have an abnormally low
620 proportion of C-phenotypes and an abnormally large proportion of N-phenotypes. Likewise,
621 the combined group of protein classes designated as “Other” in Data S11 (see Data S10 for
622 the classes included in this group) has the ratio of 73:12:15, which is significantly different
623 from the overall ratio of 62:27:11. It has an abnormally high proportion of A-phenotypes. Sheet
624 “Example comparisons” in Data S11 exemplifies significant differences between combined
625 groups. For example, the ratio of 71:18:11 for transporters is significantly different from the
626 ratio of 53:34:13 for TFs, which literally translates into a higher chance of observing a scorable
627 A-phenotype when genes under study are transporters.

628 It should be noted that 73% of A-phenotypes (group Other) is the largest proportion only within
629 Dataset S11 (differences between combined groups). Much larger proportions can be found
630 in individual classes with at least 5 genes per class (Data S10). The following classes have
631 proportions of A-phenotypes larger than 73%: Cytochrome P450 (100%, n=6), TF (bZIP
632 family) (100%, n=5); TF (NAM family) (83%, n=6), TF (C2H2 family) (80%, n=10); TF
633 (Homeobox-WOX family) (80%, n=5); and TF (MYB-HB-like family) (78%, n=18). TFs exhibit
634 a very large variation in proportions of A-phenotypes. For example, the following TF families
635 have rather low proportions: TF (SBP family) (6%, n=17); TF (C2C2-Dof family) (8%, n=13);
636 TF (Homeodomain-TALE-KNOX family) (11%, n=9); TF (ARF family) (22%, n=9); TF
637 (Hap3/NF-YB family) (27%, n=11); TF (HD-SAD family) (40%, n=5); and TF (AP2-EREBP
638 family) (43%, n=21).

639 Lastly, it is worth noting protein classes with the largest proportions of N-phenotypes (Data
640 S10): TF (C2C2-Dof family) (92%, n=13); Channel (substrate unknown) (83%, n=6); Protease
641 inhibitor (80%, n=5); Transporter (proton efflux) (60%, n=5); Membrane protein (PLAT domain
642 containing) (40%, n=5); TF (Hap3/NF-YB family) (36%, n=11); Peptide (CEP family) (25%,
643 n=8); Transporter (substrate unknown) (23%, n=13); and Enzyme (oxidoreductase) (22%,
644 n=45). Channels, regardless of the substrate, are also prominent in Dataset 11, with the
645 largest proportion of N-phenotypes among combined groups (38%, n=13).

646 In practical terms, the meta-analysis presented in this section may encourage the research
647 community to focus on classes with the higher “success rate”. However, it should not bias
648 researchers and funding agencies against candidate genes with relatively low “success rates”
649 as they can still be highly informative and useful in breeding programs and synthetic biology
650 efforts (e.g. *MtDASH*, *MtDMI1*, *MtHA1*, and many other genes in Data S6).

651 **NcORFs in *M. truncatula* genes targeted by loss-of-function approaches**

652 Due to space limitations, the entire Results section dedicated to ncORFs was placed into
653 Supporting Results, which are available in the online version of this article as a separate file.
654 This section is crucial to the message of this paper, which can be summarized as follows:
655 ncORFs cannot be ignored in functional studies as they introduce ambiguity regarding the
656 interpretation of mutant phenotypes. The section references Data S12-S18 and has its own
657 list of literature sources.

658 **DISCUSSION**

659 **The genome annotation of *M. truncatula* requires better integration of loss-of-function 660 data**

661 The latest release of the *M. truncatula* genome (v. 5.1.9) is an indispensable reference for
662 plant biologists, especially for studies that take advantage of the symbiotic properties of this

663 model organism (Pecrix et al., 2018). However, the resource lacks proper integration of
664 information on loss-of-function phenotypes. This concerns not only the detailed description of
665 phenotypes but also relevant references to loss-of-function studies (Figure 2). Consequently,
666 a researcher who considers targeting a locus of interest may be unaware of any previous work
667 on that locus. This limitation has multiple negative effects on the progress of functional
668 genomics in *M. truncatula*, including duplication of efforts, assigning multiple names to the
669 same genes, and being unable to benefit from the evidence generated in previous
670 experiments. It could be argued that obtaining such information is the responsibility of
671 researchers. However, a well-annotated and user-friendly resource should aim to facilitate
672 information retrieval, not merely leave it to the users. The tool should minimize not only the
673 effort but also the ambiguity as to which locus was affected, with little space left for
674 misinterpretation. During our meta-analysis, we have noticed that establishing a correct link
675 between a locus described in a loss-of-function study and the latest identifier of that locus is
676 not always a trivial task. Often, it requires careful sequence analysis of primers, RNAi
677 segments, and even the conversion of DNA/protein sequences from image to text. This
678 concerns not only old studies conducted before the advent of the genome browser but also
679 new studies. Our dataset can be integrated into the genome annotation of *M. truncatula* for
680 the maximal benefit of the research community.

681 **Keeping the loss-of-function domain of the browser up to date may require a human-** 682 **curated protocol**

683 Once the data becomes part of the genome browser, updating it in real time, or at least
684 frequently, presents a considerable challenge. We have noticed that many details of the
685 phenotypes and other relevant information summarized in Data S6 may be extremely difficult
686 to extract automatically. A human-curated protocol allowing direct submission may be the only
687 adequate way to record and consolidate error-free data on loss-of-function phenotypes. This,
688 however, is not a task that can be handled in a background mode by a dedicated staff member
689 of the genome browser. Integrating numerous functional genetic studies (Figure 1) can be
690 highly time-consuming, particularly given the steadily increasing number of publications each
691 year. Therefore, we propose that such information be requested directly from the authors of
692 loss-of-function studies. A convention can be established as to the rules and the format of
693 entering the information on newly characterized genes directly into the browser shortly before
694 a publication is transferred to the print stage by a journal. Each submission can have a unique
695 identifier that researchers can cite in their publications. If successful, this concept can become
696 a standard not only for *M. truncatula* but also for other species. Generalizing such a
697 submission system, however, would be the next challenge, this time of an organizational type.
698 It would require coordination between multiple institutions, resources, and publishers in such
699 a way that the journals make it compulsory for authors to register their mutant data.
700 Importantly, this should concern not only phenotypes of genes that were clearly in the focus
701 of a study (for example, their names were mentioned in a title or in an abstract) but also
702 phenotypes of mutants that had already been published in the same or a different context
703 earlier. Typically, such mutants have an auxiliary role in a study. However, they often provide
704 additional details unnoticed or not addressed in the original articles. Many phenotypes in our
705 dataset fall into this category. Data S1-S6 also list genes that were mutagenized only once;
706 however, they did not constitute the core of articles describing their phenotypes. Thus, such
707 genes can be overlooked in the literature because the fact of their mutagenesis was not
708 highlighted anywhere except for a few sentences and/or supplementary figures. Extracting
709 such information and assigning it accurately to specific loci requires a human effort that cannot
710 be easily automated.

711 The network linking the genome browsers and the journals should be the future of functional
712 genomics. It would eliminate many limitations mentioned in the previous section, thus
713 facilitating the progress of biological research. At the same time, one format described in the
714 next section can serve as a model for other resources (Baldarelli et al., 2024). It was
715 successfully implemented with an option of direct submission for mouse mutants.

716 **Strong points and limitations of existing loss-of-function databases**

717 Historically, the first attempt to create a multi-species genotype/phenotype database was
718 made at the dawn of the genomic era, before the *M. truncatula* genome became well-
719 annotated. This database, called PhenomicDB, included mouse, zebrafish, fruit fly,
720 *Caenorhabditis elegans*, yeast, and *A. thaliana* (Kahraman et al., 2005; Groth et al., 2007). It
721 contained 399,772 phenotypes associated with 77,400 genes. Unfortunately, the URL of
722 PhenomicDB, <http://www.phenomicdb.de>, has been offline since 2010. It is not available in an
723 alternative form.

724 Currently, the most advanced loss-of-function resource for animal organisms is Mouse
725 Genome Informatics (MGI) (Baldarelli et al., 2024). It is closely associated with
726 MUTAGENETIXTM, a database of N-ethyl-N-nitrosourea (ENU)-induced mutations that cause
727 phenotypes in mice (Wang et al., 2015). MGI is a well-structured, comprehensive database
728 containing information on 20,583 genes with phenotype annotations (as of 25 February 2026).
729 It enables filtering phenotypes by the mutagenesis method (the methods are not limited to the
730 treatment with ENU), allele attribute (conditional, dominant negative, no functional change,
731 etc.), type of mutation (deletion, insertion, duplication, etc.), and even the anatomical system
732 affected by the phenotype. It shows human homologs of affected genes and homologs in other
733 mammalian organisms. Importantly, the genome browser of MGI has a comprehensive
734 portfolio for each locus describing all possible aspects of corresponding mutants, including
735 references to original experimental studies. The resource accepts direct submissions of
736 phenotype data, which makes it ideal for efficient functional analysis. Its format and depth
737 should be the model for browsers of other organisms. The only drawback of the MGI browser
738 is the absence of a track for ncORFs (as of 25 February 2026), which does not permit
739 convenient checking for ncORFs potentially co-affected in mutagenesis studies. The *M.*
740 *truncatula* has such a track, with information on chimeric and non-chimeric ncORF MS-
741 validated in our study (Çakır et al., 2025b).

742 The most comprehensive analysis of loss-of-function phenotypes in a plant organism was
743 conducted in *A. thaliana* (Lloyd and Meinke, 2012). There is little to add to the deep coverage
744 of that study, which is much more versatile compared to the basic analysis we present in this
745 manuscript. The current genome browser of *A. thaliana* (Araport11, Cheng et al., 2017)
746 contains a field that summarizes loss-of-function and other important data for each affected
747 locus (Curator_summary). Unfortunately, that field contains no references to original studies
748 that established the link between a locus and its phenotype. Likewise, no details are provided
749 as to the genes potentially contributing to the phenotype. Thus, a user does not learn if the
750 phenotype is neutral, genetically conditional (more than one gene involved), or caused by a
751 single gene. Regarding the references, the *M. truncatula* genome browser is one step ahead
752 of the *A. thaliana* browser as it provides relevant references to at least some genes targeted
753 by loss-of-function approaches (Figure 2). Like the genome browser of *M. truncatula*, the *A.*
754 *thaliana* browser has a separate track for ncORFs of the following types: uORFs, dORFs, and
755 lncRNA-ORFs, according to the system of Mudge et al. (2022). In contrast to the *M. truncatula*
756 browser, the ncORF track does not include intORFs (as of 25 February 2026), presumably
757 because they are difficult to discriminate from translated refORFs by ribosome profiling (Ribo-
758 Seq). The ncORF data in the *A. thaliana* browser were generated by Wu et al. (2024a).

759 Gephebase is an excellent resource for evolutionary studies (Courtier-Orgogozo et al., 2020).
760 It focuses on genotype-phenotype relationships in natural variation observed in animals,
761 yeast, and plants. Unfortunately, the database excludes lab mutants. Other databases are
762 dedicated to mutations associated with human diseases or are much smaller in their scope
763 compared with the resources mentioned above.

764 Several platforms were developed for *in silico* mutant screening in plants. They include, but
765 are not limited to, the database of *M. truncatula* mutants (Tadege et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2018;
766 Kaur et al., 2021), TOMATOMA for tomato (Saito et al., 2011; Shikata et al., 2016), and MiRiQ
767 for rice (Kubo et al., 2024). However, these platforms cannot substitute genome browsers with
768 integrated loss-of-function data, such as MGI and Araport11, because most of the mutants
769 listed in those databases have not been characterized yet.

770 These considerations position our resource as smaller in scale than the *A. thaliana* database,
771 but still essential for plant biologists, as it represents the most comprehensive loss-of-function
772 dataset available after *A. thaliana*. Importantly, the integration of ncORF information with
773 functional data gives our dataset a unique value among comparable resources. Specifically,
774 among all standard genome browsers, only the browsers of *A. thaliana* and *M. truncatula* have
775 the ncORF tracks (Wu et al., 2024a; Çakır et al., 2025b). In contrast to the *Arabidopsis*
776 browser, our ncORF track in the *Medicago* browser includes MS-validated ncORFs that are
777 embedded in refORFs or overlap with refORFs (ncORF designated as “intORFs”, “uoORFs”,
778 and “doORFs” in the system of Mudge et al., 2022), along with all other major ncORF types.
779 Lastly, the *Medicago* ncORF track is currently the only one (globally) that includes chimeric
780 ncORFs (ncORFs that are translated to chimeric peptides via programmed ribosomal
781 frameshifting, PRF).

782 **About the content of Supporting Discussion**

783 Due to space limitations, many important considerations about loss-of-function data, as well
784 as about ambiguities associated with ncORFs and *Tnt1*, were placed into a separate file
785 named Supporting Discussion. The file references Figure 4, supporting Figures S6-S9,
786 supporting Tables S2 and S3, Data S19, and has its own list of literature sources. Figure 4
787 introduces seven types of ambiguity associated with translated ncORFs in loss-of-function
788 studies, with real examples.

789 **The take-home message**

790 Functional genomics relies upon comprehensive and accurate annotation of genes available
791 as a genome browser. At the same time, a truly comprehensive genome browser should
792 encompass the information on loss-of-function phenotypes. While the mouse, *A. thaliana*, and
793 *M. truncatula* genomes are among the few to link such information to specific loci, there is
794 currently no standard pipeline for systematic recording, storage, and displaying phenotypic
795 data for other organisms. Here, we propose developing a centralized system that should make
796 it obligatory for researchers to report such information at the publication stage. We also
797 showed the limitations of the most comprehensive genome browsers, which can be
798 summarized as the lack of information on genes co-affected in original studies (multiple
799 knockouts or knockdowns) and missing references to such studies. Besides, the main purpose
800 of this work was to show that two fundamental aspects of functional genome annotation have
801 been largely overlooked in standard genome browsers. These aspects are (1) translated and
802 conserved ncORFs and (2) trans effects of insertional mutagenesis on splicing. Although both
803 phenomena have been well documented, they remain beyond consideration in nearly all
804 functional analyses. We provided examples of how overlooking such information may result
805 in major misinterpretation of loss-of-function phenotypes.

806 Importantly, this ambiguity is not unique to *M. truncatula*. It represents a pervasive, often
807 ignored variable in plant functional genomics. Whether using RNAi, which inevitably targets
808 co-transcribed ncORFs, or gene editing via CRISPR/Cas9, which can disrupt overlapping
809 coding sequences or splicing motifs, the “one gene, one phenotype” assumption is frequently
810 violated. Our data highlight that a significant proportion of “verified” mutants likely requires re-
811 evaluation to rule out ncORF contributions. Thus, the framework presented here serves not
812 merely as a curatorial resource, but as a necessary quality-control step for distinguishing
813 causal refORF mutations from ncORF-mediated artifacts in genetic studies.

814 We also showed how ncORFs can help rectify doubtful gene models. Despite the relatively
815 modest scope of the genome browser of *M. truncatula*, the integration of loss-of-function and
816 ncORF data in one resource can make it even more useful. In addition to summarizing the
817 information on phenotypes of 673 genes in the present manuscript, we mapped 805 non-
818 chimeric and 156 chimeric MS-validated ncORFs to corresponding loci in the genome
819 browser. To the best of our knowledge, after the ncORF study conducted in *Arabidopsis* (Wu
820 et al., 2024a), this is the second study to merge loss-of-function data with ncORFs in any
821 organism. At the same time, it is the first attempt to reconsider published loss-of-function
822 phenotypes in the light of knowledge about translated ncORFs expressed from the same loci.
823 We expect that this resource will serve as the model for browsers of other organisms, which
824 will ultimately improve the quality of functional analyses for the maximal benefit of biomedical
825 research, sustainable agriculture, and biotechnology.

826 Our meta-analysis of loss-of-function studies produced unique data on family-wise proportions
827 of altered, conditional, and neutral phenotypes in different protein classes and families. This
828 type of resolution is so far unprecedented because other studies mostly reported frequencies
829 of essential genes only for heterogeneous classes that combine members of diverse families.
830 Our list of tripartite phenotype proportions can be used by legume biologists and breeders as
831 a cheat sheet to focus on candidate genes that are likely to give a scorable phenotype. We
832 explicitly state that such a resource may have validity only within the legume family or even
833 *M. truncatula* alone. Like any cheat sheet, it should be used constructively: gene families with
834 low proportions of altered phenotypes should not be deprived of due attention.

835 The manuscript also coins several ideas in the field of ncORFomics. To the best of our
836 knowledge, these ideas are novel. First, based on earlier reviews and our new data, we
837 developed, discussed, and exemplified the classification of ambiguities associated with
838 ncORFs in loss-of-function studies. Second, we explained why the analysis of taxonomic
839 ranges of ncProts’ conservation should become a standard component of genome
840 annotations. Third, we advocated the potential biological relevance of ncProts whose
841 conservation signatures are limited to the species of origin. Fourth, we showed how certain
842 translated ncORFs can systematically remain undetected due to regions of 100% similarity to
843 refProts in the species of origin. Lastly, we provided examples in which very strong
844 conservation of ncORFs at the amino acid level may not be a reliable marker of their
845 translation. These considerations will help better understand the biological roles of ncORFs,
846 separately from refORFs, as an integral component of the organismal translome.

847 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

848 **Meta-analysis of loss-of-function studies**

849 Literature on loss-of-function studies in *M. truncatula* was collected manually using Google
850 Scholar, PubMed, and other search engines. Main texts and supplementary data were
851 examined for information on locus identifiers, short and long forms of locus names,
852 mutagenesis systems, loss-of-function phenotypes, and protein classes. The protein class of

853 each entry was reconfirmed with the *M. truncatula* genome browser (Pecrix et al., 2018) and
854 the UniProt reference protein database (UniProt Consortium, 2019). The correspondence
855 between the latest locus identifiers and identifiers from earlier versions of the genome release
856 was established in various ways, depending on the availability of the primary information in
857 original studies. For some entries, the current locus identifiers were deduced using BLASTN
858 (Altschul et al., 1990; Boratyn et al., 2013) analysis of primers and/or RNAi segments, BLASTP
859 (Altschul et al., 1990; Boratyn et al., 2013) analysis of protein sequences, and sometimes
860 required the conversion of images to text for the extraction of sequence information. All steps
861 were manually curated, free of artificial intelligence.

862 **Detection of ncORFs**

863 Conserved and MS-validated ncORFs were detected using MosaicProt (Çakır et al., 2025c).
864 In short, each annotated transcript was scanned for the presence of stop-free regions longer
865 than 59 nt in all forward reading frames. Such regions were *in silico* translated, supplied with
866 unique informative identifiers, and saved in FASTA format. RefProts were separated from
867 ncProts by matching each sequence to the currently annotated list of refProts.

868 For conservation analysis, all ncProts were compared with UniProt v. 2020_02 entries (UniProt
869 Consortium, 2019) using DIAMOND v. 0.9.14 (Buchfink et al., 2021). NcProts with at least one
870 match, including matches to *M. truncatula* sequences only, were categorized as conserved if
871 the e-value of the top match was not more than 0.001. We explicitly declare that our definition
872 of conserved ncProts is conditional in this study. It does not imply multi-species conservation,
873 although some ncProts are conserved across hundreds of species.

874 For MS-validation of ncProts, they were compared to MS peptides from three publicly
875 deposited proteomic datasets (PXD002692, Marx et al., 2016; PXD013606, Shin et al., 2021;
876 and PXD022278, Castañeda et al., 2021), 16 samples in total, using SearchGUI v. 4.0.41
877 (Barsnes & Vaudel, 2018) and its partner tool PeptideShaker v. 2.0.33 (Vaudel et al., 2015).
878 Each sample was searched independently using the target-decoy approach with FDR below
879 1%. MS peptides matching refProts and/or common contaminants were filtered out. The
880 detection of NCR169 serves as a positive control for our procedure. NCR169 is a well-
881 characterized peptide crucial for SNF (Starker et al., 2006; Domonkos et al., 2013; Farkas et
882 al., 2014; Horváth et al., 2015, 2023; Güngör et al., 2023; Li et al., 2025).

883 MS-validated non-chimeric and chimeric ncProts (805 and 156, respectively) were mapped to
884 the current genome and are available in the genome browser as two separate tracks (Çakır et
885 al., 2025b). For chimeric MS peptides, not only 145 primary sources but also 101 potential
886 alternative sources were mapped. The primary sources are loci in which chimeric MS peptides
887 were identified in our analysis. Alternative sources of the same peptides were found using the
888 ChiMSource software (Çakır et al., 2025a). Which of the loci are the true sources of chimeric
889 MS-validated peptides was discussed in Çakır et al. (2025b). For 805 non-chimeric MS-
890 validated peptides, we found 833 potential sources, which are mapped in the genome browser.

891 **Locating mutations and insertions relative to refORFs and ncORFs of affected genes**

892 To determine whether refORFs and selected ncORFs were affected in the original studies, we
893 analyzed images and sequence data presented by the authors. In some cases, the exact
894 positions of *Tnt1* insertions were deduced from FST sequences downloaded from the *Tnt1*
895 mutant database of *M. truncatula* (Tadege et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2018; Kaur et al., 2021).
896 Exon-intron maps of gene models were prepared by aligning cDNA to genomic DNA in
897 Geneious® (MUSCLE alignment), with the manual correction of alignment artifacts at the
898 splicing sites.

899 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

900 **Umut Çakır:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis,
901 Resources, Data Curation, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing,
902 Visualization, Funding acquisition. **Noujoud Gabed:** Conceptualization, Validation, Formal
903 analysis, Resources, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Selen Kaya:** Investigation,
904 Data Curation. **Vagner A. Benedito:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing. **Marie**
905 **Brunet:** Methodology. **Xavier Roucou:** Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing. **Igor S.**
906 **Kryvoruchko:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Resources, Data
907 Curation, Investigation, Software, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing,
908 Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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920 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

921 The annotated models of 123 genes listed in Data S12 are available in Geneious® format in
922 the online version of this article (Data S18). They include cDNA and gDNA sequences,
923 refORFs and ncORFs mapped to cDNA sequences, and alignments of cDNA and gDNA,
924 which outline exon-intron structures of the models. The entire set of files for the conservation
925 evidence and MS-validation of ncProts will be published later in a paper describing all
926 conserved and translated ncProts detected in *M. truncatula*. On 8 January 2025, our data were
927 integrated into the *M. truncatula* genome portal MtrunA17r5.0-ANR as a separate track. In
928 total, 156 MS-validated chimeric peptides were mapped to 246 primary and alternative source
929 loci in the genome browser (non-repeat-element alternative sources only). In addition, 805
930 MS-validated non-chimeric ncProts were mapped to 833 genomic loci. The complete set of
931 data related to this article is available from the digital repository Zenodo. The codes used in
932 this study are accessible from the following GitHub repository:
933 github.com/umutcakir/ncORFs_in_studied_genes_of_Medicago_truncatula

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1360 **Table 1.** Description of the core datasets

Dataset	Locus type	Phenotypes	Type of functional characterization	Number of loci [†] , LOF	Number of loci [†] , GOF only
Data S1	RefORFs	Non-SNF	LOF	508 (501)	-
Data S2	NcORFs	Non-SNF	LOF, GOF	11 (11)	16 (15)
Data S3	RefORFs	SNF	LOF	354 (351)	-
Data S4	NcORFs	SNF	LOF, GOF	30 (30)	18 (17)
Data S5 [‡]	RefORFs and ncORFs	Non-SNF and SNF	LOF	222 (219)	-
Data S6 [§]	RefORFs and ncORFs	Non-SNF and SNF	LOF	681 (673)	-

[†]Numbers in brackets correspond to unique loci for which the identifiers in v5.1.9 are known.

[‡]Data S5 lists only those genes that were tested for both non-SNF and SNF phenotypes.

[§]Data S6 lists all genes.

Abbreviations:

RefORFs – reference open reading frames

NcORFs – non-canonical open reading frames

LOF – loss-of-function phenotypes

GOF – gain-of-function phenotypes

SNF – symbiotic nitrogen fixation phenotypes

1361

1362 **Table 2.** Description of the supporting datasets

Dataset	Description
Data S7	References for LOF studies only (refORFs and ncORFs)
Data S8	References for GOF studies only (ncORFs only)
Data S9	The complete list of 97 biological processes examined in LOF studies
Data S10	The complete list of protein classes, corresponding phenotype counts, and statistical analysis of proportions
Data S11	The complete list of combined protein groups, corresponding phenotype counts, and statistical analysis of proportions
Data S12	A master table that summarizes various parameters of 148 ncORFs found in 123 genes targeted by functional analyses
Data S13	Visual demonstration of conservation at the amino acid level for eight selected ncORFs

- Data S14 Evidence for purifying selection of the eight selected ncORFs
 Data S15 24 nucleotide alignments that demonstrate evidence for purifying selection of the eight selected ncORFs
 Data S16 Sequence analysis demonstrating the origin of highly conserved ncORFs in five selected genes
 Data S17 Nucleotide alignments used in Data S16
 Data S18 Gene models and mapped ncORFs of 123 loci targeted by functional analyses in *M. truncatula* (Data S12)
 Data S19 NcProts grouped with refProts during the MS analysis

1363

1364 **Table 3.** Loci incorrectly named in the genome browser v. 5.1.9

Name [†]	Actual locus ID (publication)	Publication
<i>MtCbf4</i>	MtrunA17_Chr1g0203861	Zhang et al., 2016b
<i>MtChOMT1</i> [‡]	MtrunA17_Chr1g0200491	Wu et al., 2024b
<i>MtGA20ox1</i>	MtrunA17_Chr1g0204181	Li et al., 2021b
<i>MtHDT3</i>	MtrunA17_Chr7g0265761	Li et al., 2021a
<i>MtMYC2</i>	MtrunA17_Chr8g0366751	Guo et al., 2024
<i>MtPRP1</i> [‡]	MtrunA17_Chr4g0013391	Erickson et al., 2020
<i>MtPRR7</i>	MtrunA17_Chr1g0181811	Wang et al., 2023
<i>MtRac1</i>	MtrunA17_Chr6g0486041	Wang et al., 2021
<i>MtROP9</i>	MtrunA17_Chr5g0405791	Kiirika et al., 2012
<i>MtSCR</i>	MtrunA17_Chr7g0245601	Dong et al., 2021
<i>MtSLB1</i>	MtrunA17_Chr5g0447381	Yin et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2021

[†]The table lists correct names and corresponding locus identifiers. These names were incorrectly assigned to other loci in the genome browser v. 5.1.9.

[‡]Names *MtChOMT1* and *MtPRP1* were misassigned to two genes each in the genome browser v. 5.1.9.

Table S1 provides an extended version of this list.

1365

1366

1367 **Figure 1.** Timeline of loss-of-function studies in *Medicago truncatula*. The graph is based on
 1368 the first publication of each genetic locus, 673 loci in total. 219 of these genes were studied in
 1369 the context of both symbiotic nitrogen fixation (SNF) and other processes. 380 loci were tested
 1370 for SNF phenotypes and 512 for non-SNF phenotypes. On average, ca. 47 new genes have
 1371 been characterized each year since 2020 (2025 excluded). The complete dataset consists of
 1372 565 published works and bioRxiv preprints as of 16 June 2025.

1373

1374 **Figure 2.** Functional annotation status of 673 genes studied by loss-of-function approaches
 1375 in *M. truncatula*, based on the genome browser v. 5.1.9. (a) Six categories of loci based on
 1376 their annotation status. The first element in each category's code corresponds to a gene name
 1377 ("Yes" - name assigned, "No" - name not assigned). More than one quarter (26%) of
 1378 characterized genes are not named (Data S6 Column V). The second element in each
 1379 category's code corresponds to a reference ("Yes" - reference assigned, "No" - reference not
 1380 assigned, "YN" for "Yes and No" - an irrelevant reference assigned). More than one quarter
 1381 (27%) of characterized genes have no reference (Data S6 Column W). Among genes with a
 1382 reference, 32% have only irrelevant references or references to transcriptomic studies/reviews
 1383 instead of correct references to loss-of-function studies. (b) The distribution of 173 "missed"
 1384 genes over their publication years (category "No/No", no name and no reference in the
 1385 genome browser v. 5.1.9). Only the year of the first loss-of-function publication is counted for
 1386 each gene.

Total count	A, count	C, count	N, count	A, proportion	C, proportion	N, proportion	Protein class
48	34	13	1	71	27	2	Enzyme (kinase)
45	25	10	10	56	22	22	Enzyme (oxidoreductase)
43	29	13	1	67	30	2	Enzyme (transferase)
39	22	16	1	56	41	3	Enzyme (hydrolase)
21	9	12	0	43	57	0	TF (AP2-EREBP family)
19	11	6	2	58	32	11	TF (GRAS family)
18	14	4	0	78	22	0	TF (MYB-HB-like family)
17	1	16	0	6	94	0	TF (SBP family)
13	1	0	12	8	0	92	TF (C2C2-Dof family)
13	5	5	3	38	38	23	Transporter (substrate unknown)
12	8	3	1	67	25	8	TF (MADS-MIKC family)
11	3	4	4	27	36	36	TF (Hap3/NF-YB family)
10	5	3	2	50	30	20	F-box protein
10	8	1	1	80	10	10	TF (C2H2 family)
9	6	2	1	67	22	11	Peptide (cysteine-rich, NCR family)
9	2	7	0	22	78	0	TF (ARF family)
9	6	2	1	67	22	11	TF (bHLH family)
9	1	7	1	11	78	11	TF (Homeodomain-TALE-KNOX family)
8	4	4	0	50	50	0	Enzyme (ligase)
8	1	5	2	13	63	25	Peptide (CEP family)
302	224	46	32	74	15	11	Other
673	419	179	75	62	27	11	All

1387

1388 **Figure 3.** Different protein classes have different proportions of phenotypes, which may reflect
 1389 their relative functional importance. Letters A, C, and N stand for altered, conditional, and
 1390 neutral phenotypes, respectively. The graph shows only the top-20 protein classes. The

1391 complete list of protein classes and corresponding statistical analysis are available in Data
 1392 S10. The summary on phenotypes of combined protein groups is available in Data S11.

1393

1394 **Figure 4.** Main types of ambiguity associated with translated ncORFs in loss-of-function
 1395 studies. Ambiguity types are exemplified based on the assumption that currently annotated
 1396 gene models are correct. Each column corresponds to a specific location of a ncORF relative
 1397 to its refORF (uORFs, uoORFs, intORFs, doORFs, and dORFs, respectively, Mudge et al.,
 1398 2022). Each row corresponds to a specific scenario leading to the inactivation of one or two
 1399 ORFs. The graph is a simplified illustration of the most common scenarios. It does not apply
 1400 to the following situations: (1) a mutation outside both ORFs affects their transcription or
 1401 translation without affecting their amino acid sequences; (2) an insertion at one location

1402 interferes with splicing at a different location, thus affecting ORFs in trans. Abbreviations: UTR,
1403 untranslated region; RNAi, RNA interference; PTGS, post-transcriptional gene silencing.

1404 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

1405 Additional Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

1406 **Figure S1.** Loss-of-function approaches used for studying 673 genes in *Medicago truncatula*.

1407 **Figure S2.** Biological processes examined in loss-of-function studies on 673 genes in
1408 *Medicago truncatula*.

1409 **Figure S3.** Different groups of protein classes have different proportions of phenotypes, which
1410 may reflect their relative functional importance.

1411 **Figure S4.** Partitioning of phenomics data into altered (A), conditional (C), and neutral (N)
1412 phenotypes.

1413 **Figure S5.** Phenotypes of 219 genes studied in the context of both symbiotic nitrogen fixation
1414 (SNF) and other processes.

1415 **Figure S6.** Aberrant transcript forms recovered from two *Tnt1* mutant lines of *MtSWEET11*
1416 (Kryvoruchko et al., 2016).

1417 **Figure S7.** Frequencies of aberrant transcript forms recovered from two *Tnt1* mutant lines
1418 shown in Figure S6.

1419 **Figure S8.** A ClustalW protein alignment of the mutant version of *MtSWEET11* (Type X) with
1420 the wild-type version from ecotype R108 (the background of the *Tnt1* mutant population).

1421 **Figure S9.** Biological and biosafety implications of induced insertional mutagenesis.

1422 **Table S1.** Loci incorrectly named in the genome browser v. 5.1.9 (an extended version of
1423 Table 3).

1424 **Table S2.** Five v4 gene models that may be correct without splitting.

1425 **Table S3.** MS-validated ncORFs that introduce ambiguity into the interpretation of loss-of-
1426 function studies.

1427 **Data S1.** A master table that summarizes loss-of-function studies on mRNA-refORFs and
1428 ncRNAs tested for phenotypes other than symbiotic nitrogen fixation.

1429 **Data S2.** A master table that summarizes loss-of-function and gain-of-function studies on
1430 ncORFs tested for phenotypes other than symbiotic nitrogen fixation.

1431 **Data S3.** A master table that summarizes loss-of-function studies on mRNA-refORFs and
1432 ncRNAs tested for symbiotic nitrogen fixation phenotypes.

1433 **Data S4.** A master table that summarizes loss-of-function and gain-of-function studies on
1434 ncORFs tested for symbiotic nitrogen fixation phenotypes.

1435 **Data S5.** A master table that summarizes loss-of-function studies on mRNA-refORFs,
1436 ncRNAs, and ncORFs tested for both symbiotic nitrogen fixation (SNF) and non-SNF
1437 phenotypes.

1438 **Data S6.** A master table that summarizes loss-of-function studies on 673 loci in *Medicago*
1439 *truncatula*.

- 1440 **Data S7.** A list of 565 loss-of-function studies on mRNA-refORFs, ncRNAs, and ncORFs in
1441 *Medicago truncatula*.
- 1442 **Data S8.** A list of 37 gain-of-function and other non-mutant studies on ncORFs/peptides in
1443 *Medicago truncatula*.
- 1444 **Data S9.** The complete list of 97 biological processes examined in loss-of-function studies on
1445 673 genes in *Medicago truncatula*.
- 1446 **Data S10.** The complete list of protein classes, corresponding phenotype counts, and
1447 statistical analysis of proportions.
- 1448 **Data S11.** The complete list of combined protein groups, corresponding phenotype counts,
1449 and statistical analysis of proportions.
- 1450 **Data S12.** A master table that summarizes various parameters of 148 ncORFs found in 123
1451 genes targeted by functional analyses in *Medicago truncatula*.
- 1452 **Data S13.** Visual demonstration of conservation at the amino acid level for eight selected
1453 ncORFs.
- 1454 **Data S14.** Evidence for purifying selection of eight selected ncORFs.
- 1455 **Data S15.** 24 nucleotide alignments that demonstrate evidence for purifying selection of eight
1456 selected ncORFs.
- 1457 **Data S16.** Sequence analysis demonstrating the origin of highly conserved ncORFs in five
1458 selected genes.
- 1459 **Data S17.** Nucleotide alignments used in Data S16.
- 1460 **Data S18.** Gene models and mapped ncORFs of 123 loci targeted by functional analyses in
1461 *Medicago truncatula* (Data S12).
- 1462 **Data S19.** NcProts grouped with refProts during the MS analysis.